

Users' Perception of the Library Automation: A Brief Study in Library Automation

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Abstract:- The article highlights users' perception of library automation this research paper focuses on the guidance of the libraries automation also the transfer environment of the libraries' supervision. The effect of information communication technology has altered the libraries' operations and their functions into an acrimonious. They just get their document seen on the front of their laptop & computer. Automation has diminished manpower. This research will discuss the various components that help automation in libraries. A few software has been given which are existing for the library automation, its requirement, library housekeeping works.

Keywords:- Library, Software, Housekeeping work, Automation.

I. INTRODUCTION

This change in the libraries has brought new thinking to library automatism. It is a fateful factor in any academic society it is the center of the education & learning activation where users can find massive resources. The computer is being used for housekeeping works of the libraries, it saves the moment of the professional librarians as well and at the equal moment cast repeat of thing and makes the library services emphatic. In the era of information communication technology, the library underplot has been drastically altered in the precondition of accumulation simultaneously, company & services readers' demand and attitude having altered in the kind. Also, the acquaintance-seek experience of the readers has dynamic altered. This notion has posed a challenge for the library professional librarians for accelerated dealing of the libraries' services.

II. THE MEANING OF THE LIBRARY AUTOMATION

The word "Automation" has been derived from the Greek word "auto mode" which means something, which has the power of spontaneous motion or self-movement. The term "automation" was first introduced by D.S.Harder 1936, who was then with General Motor Company in the U.S. used the term automation to mean automatic handling of parts between progressive production processes. Dr. Jhon Shaw Billing a Librarian started the entire automation process in our society (Rayward, 2002). The idea for punched card equipment was suggested by Dr. Billing, the then librarian of the surgeon general's library, according to Herman Hollerith a census bureau employee who designed it. Hollerith formed the tabulating machine company in 1896, which later become the international Business Machines (IBM) corporation one of the largest organizations in the computer industry (Mukhopadhyay, 2005).

III. TERM OF THE LIBRARY AUTOMATISM

Automation is a rise of work from action through the mediums. To reuse the main power and time. COMPUTER-INPUT-PROCESS-OUTPUT.

Automation is the stage of using mechanism for easy operative and saving human being entity and moment.

Ethically to the Oxford English dictionary automation is the "Application of automatic control to any branch of industry or science by extension the use of the electronic or mechanical devices to science by extension the use of electronic or mechanical devices to replace human labor". (Simpson & Weiner, 1989).

The libraries automation is the applications of the computer & exploitation of computer-founded products & employ in the performances of apart the library manipulation and works in the regulation of different execution and output products'.

IV. THE OBJECTIVE STUDIES

- To find out readers are aware of the libraries' automation.
- Find out the influence of automation on library housekeeping function upon the application by her libraries also the educational works by the readers.
- Get uses suggestions for antecedent correction.
- To find readers' scarification with library automation.
- To examine the librarians' role in automation-related decision-making.

V. NEED AND OBJECTIVES LIBRARY AUTOMATION

Nowadays no the readers have time to search for the required and relevant pieces of an acquaintance from the compact hoard of advice accumulation. So it pins down library automation. Must library is to be automated/automation. The different components that constrain changing directed library systems and automated/automation libraries systems are as adhere.

- Record-deferment activities' of the library can be done successfully in an automation atmosphere.
- Issued comeback & renovation of books may be featured and cast about of documents care of the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) is a dominant instrument of the libraries automatism.
- It will expense Influence.
- Preserve a Bibliographical recording of each the equipment in a computer-razed form.
- Slacken the replication in the manufacturing procedure of housekeeping works.
- Endue entry stand for knowledge at a fast wages.

- Reduce replication in the manufacturing processes of the housekeeping works.
- Share and the resource through library networking & execution of new IT processes to supply -attribute knowledge.

VI. INTERRUPTION TO LIBRARIES AUTOMATION

They could get some thinkable inhibition to library automation.

- Fear of antagonistic effect on professional employment.
- The library's staff have to undergo extensive training.
- Suspicion that the processing could be too costly.
- Scarcity of decency from the management is thinkable per budget impaction.
- The professionals are in the beginning psychologically traced.

VII. WHAT IS THE AUTOMATION?

All common manufactured and service of the library beable automated heed of the library automation. Sans in a

- Dissemination of Information
- (ILL) Inter-Library Loan
- (SV) Stock Verification

some libraries automation soft wares packages there are provision stand for paragraph arrangement, abstract outset.

VIII. THE ONLINE PUBLIC ACCESS CATALOGUE (OPAC)

- Circulation /Expenditure
- Acquisition /Acquirement
- Serial-Control/Command
- Internet
- Automatism / Digital Library

IX. AUTOMATION LIBRARIES HELPING HAND

There are different many more of the automatism services stored by the automation libraries. These are library automation good turn are:

- (CAS) Current Awareness Services
- (OSS) Online Search Service
- (P I) Printed Indexes
- (SDI)

Selective

- (RS) Reference Service
- (HW) Housekeeping Work
- (PI) Printed Indexes

Figure 7: Structure of library automation system

Fig. 1: Library Automation System

X. REQUIREMENT FOR THE LIBRARIES AUTOMATION

The underlying requirement for any the libraries automation/automated programmer is the Software, Hardware, and Man-power Finances.

XI. AS WELL AS HARDWARE

The hardware is the forward fateful inwardness by the libraries automatism schedule figure of production and builder existing in order to this intention. The hardware endowment principally related to on the soft wares. There are two types of PCs are acquirable in the marketplace like.

- The brand PCs from reputable firm like HP, Compaq, IBM, ET.
- The anthologized PC by mercantile firm.

XII. AS WELL AS SOFTWARES

The accomplishment of the library automation chiefly be dependent on the disposition of the software applied in order to the reason.

The clear cut types of available the library soft wares are of the under mentioned types.

- In home flourish soft wares or custom-designed.
- Software packages develop by mercantile agency, organization and institution.
- Co-operative trading.

Therefore the collecting of good library soft wares are one of the part important functions of a library automatism schedule. But it should be select deferment in nous the requirement of the round up.

A list of some the library automation soft wares are given down.

SOME SOFTWARES	SOME SOFTWARES
1. Acquis	28. Library Manager
2. Archives	29. LIBRIS
3. Ascat	30. LIBSOFT
4. ASCIR	31. LIBSYS
5. ASIRE	32. List Plus
6. Biblosis	33. Loan Soft
7. CAT-MAN	34. Martyrs
8. CDS/ISIS	35. MEC-SYS
9. CLMS	36. Min ISIS
10. DATA TREK	37. NILIS
11. Defiance Library Managementsystem	38. Nirmals
12. Del-DOS	39. PALMS
13. Del-MARC	40. SALIM
14. Delsis	41. Sanjay
15. Del-Window	42. SERAS
16. Easylib	43. SLIM
17. Golden LIBRA	44. SOUL
18. Granthalya	45. SUCHIKA
19. ILMS	46. Techlib
20. Krvger Library	47. Telelib
21. LIB-AMS	48. TLMS
22. Libsoft	49. TRISHNA
23. Liberator	50. TULIB
24. LIBMAN	51. TULIPS
25. Micro Libsys	52. ULYSIS
26. Librarian	53. WILSYS
27. Library Management	54. WIN/SIS

XIII. PROBLEMS WITH AUTOMATISM

There are many vested subjects appurtenant with the library automation programmers. The subject can be brief down.

- Preparatory penetration in order to automation programmers is much advanced.
- The Library personnel has to elapse deep exercitation in Automation.
- The vocational is at the beginning psychologically trace.
- Different departments of the company require to be orderly for the prosperous running of the programmers.
- Retrospectively modification of data for the large libraries.
- Periodic expenditure needs to bear doubtless approval from the authorizations.

XIV. AS WELL AS THE CONCLUSION

An automated library can supply preferable library services to its readers and librarians. Now library automation has become the buzzword. The Record-housekeeping activities descent be very easily in an automated library method. An automation library can confer a computer-based version of the library management system which will advantage the readers, librarians, and also the panel members the library can't and save the impotent time also reduce the effort resources. But the property of any library's automation programs depends on its suitable mapping also performance. Hence the libraries' professional librarians' are required to tack the correct initiative in the right way.

XV. THE FUTURE SCOPE

- Self-check-in or check-out in the first instance for oneself-issued and comeback of books in the library without the help of library personnel.
- Advanced fine clearance method can be amassed.
- Thieveries' ascertain.

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